

First record of *Aradus flavicornis* Dalman, 1823 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Aradidae) for Cyprus

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ABSTRACT: The first record of *Aradus flavicornis* Dalman, 1823 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Aradidae) for Cyprus is reported. The distribution of the species in the Mediterranean Region is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Aradus flavicornis*, first record, distribution, Cyprus, Mediterranean Region.

Aradus flavicornis Dalman, 1823 and Tunisia in North Africa and from (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Aradidae) is a Sinai and the Asian part of Türkiye in Palearctic species which is present in Asia (Aukema, 2024), so far. North Africa, Asia and Europe (Extralimital: Afrotropical Region). In the Mediterranean Region, the species has been reported from Albania, Andorra, Croatia, France (mainland and Corsica), Greece (mainland and Crete), Italy, Malta, Portugal, Spain (mainland and Balearic Islands) and Türkiye (European part) in Europe, from Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco

Heiss & Péricart (2007) mentioned Cyprus as a presumable part of the distribution range of *A. flavicornis*, but no record from the island has been reported, yet.

Now, the first record of *A. flavicornis* for Cyprus can be reported: On 12.09.2024, an adult specimen was observed and

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photographed near the village of Chirokitia, located in the district of Larnaca in the south-eastern part of Cyprus.

The specimen was attracted by the artificial light of an actinic fluorescent tube (Benoît Segerer, pers. comm.) A photo of the specimen (Fig. 1) was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Segerer, 2024).

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Aradus flavicornis* Dalman, 1823, near Chirokitia, Cyprus, 12.09.2024. (Photo: Benoît Segerer).